

Plant Parasitic Nematodes and Fungi spp Associated with Yam Rot (*Dioscorea rotundata*) from Selected Yam Stands in Yenagoa Metropolis, Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Postharvest spoilage of yam has been attributed to nematode and fungal infestation, yet this information is lacking in the Yenagoa metropolis of Bayelsa State. The study was undertaken to assess the prevalence of nematodes and fungi on stored yams in the Yenagoa metropolis. Selected tubers of yam of the species *Dioscorea rotundata* suspected to be infected with nematodes were priced and bought from selected yam stands. The yams were transported to the Biology Laboratory, Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State, where they were processed for nematode and fungi analyses. The preparation and analyses of the yam for parasites and microbial analyses followed standard procedures. A five (5)-fold serial dilution method was adopted for microbial culture, while a modified rubber bow techniques was adopted for nematodes extraction. The morphological identification of the plant parasitic nematodes and fungi followed standard keys. From the results, three (3) parasitic nematodes in three genera were recovered from the yam. The nematodes in order of their abundance were *Scutellonema spp* (50%), *Meloidogyne spp* (30%), and *Pratylenus spp*. (20%). The abundance of the plant parasitic nematodes varied across location ($p < 0.05$). The percentage prevalence of the fungi species recovered from the yam in order of increasing occurrences are *Aspergillus niger* (25.8%), *Aspergillus flavus* (25.8%), *Alternarium alternata* (19.9%), *Rhizopus stolonifera* (15.2%), and the least was *Penicillium spp* (9.9%). The differences in the species-specific fungi were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The interaction of nematodes and fungi takes a similar pattern across the study locations. In all locations, at least one parasite and fungus were recovered from the rotten yam. However, the species of nematodes associating with fungi differs from location to location. However, in all cases, nematodes were found to have initiated the yam rot before fungi invasion.

Keywords: Nematodes, Fungi, *Dioscorea rotundata*, Yam storage, Yenagoa metropolis,

INTRODUCTION

Yam (family: Dioscoreaceae) is a perennial herbaceous vine cultivated mainly for the consumption of its starchy tubers (Okigbo, 2004). In Africa's tropics and subtropics, it is among the most vital staple foods (Okigbo & Ogonnaya, 2006). Although other yam species have been found worldwide, the *Dioscorea rotundata* (white yam), *Dioscorea cayenensis* (yellow yam), and *Dioscorea alata* (water yam) are the most widely grown in Nigeria (Onyeka et al., 2011). Millions of people in Sub-Saharan Africa rely on these

edible yam cultivars as a major source of carbohydrates, making them significant food crops (Anon 2009).

Yam production has increased steadily in the last decades from 18 million metric tons in 1990 to a current estimate of approximately 39 million metric tons (FAO, 2001). West Africa produces more than 90% of the yams consumed worldwide. Three-quarters of the world's yam production comes from Nigeria alone (Okigbo, 2004). According to reports, insect infestation causes over 40% of Africa's root and tuber crops to decay each year (Anon. 2009). According to Nwachukwu and Osuji (2008), these bacteria result in significant losses in produce quantity as well as numerous additional effects on produce quality.

On the one hand, worm and fungal infestations, and on the other, the conditions of the storage facilities, have been blamed for postharvest yam deterioration. For farmers, post-harvest rot of roots and tubers has been a major issue because it can cause over 40% of their harvest to deteriorate (Okigbo *et al.*, 2004). In many regions of the world, the issue has been made worse by a lack of debt research and capacity training in yam-based studies (Onyeka *et al.*, 2011; Taiga, 2011). Identification of micro-organisms during and after post-harvest is germane for the initiation of control measures (Okigbo & Odurukwe, 2009). However, this information is lacking in the Yenagoa metropolis of Bayelsa State. The study was aimed at investigating the prevalence of nematodes and fungi associated with yam rot in some selected yam stands in Yenagoa metropolis.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Study area

The study was conducted using the same species of yam known as *Dioscorea rotundata*. The study was conducted in four communities: Yenegue-gene, Tombia, Swali, and Opolo. These communities are all located within the Yenagoa metropolis (Latitude 4°52'3.9972, Longitude 5°53'55.3704). The coordinates of the study locations are Yenegue-gene (latitude 4°56'37.9, longitude 6°19'35.5); Tombia (Latitude 4°49'26.76", Longitude 6° 59'39.8004); Swali (Latitude 4.9186438, Longitude 6.2672831) and Opolo (Latitude 4°56'48, Longitude 6°20'16") respectively.

Procurement and processing of yam samples

Two yam stands were randomly selected from the study communities. Two tubers of yam suspected to be infected were priced and bought. The species of all yam bought was *Dioscorea rotundata*. This species of yam was selected because they were more in supply at the time of the study. The yam samples were transported to the Department of Biological Sciences/Microbiology for parasitological and microbial analyses.

Microbial analysis

The spot foci for fungal infestation in the yam were identified. The yams were peeled to expose the rot tissues. Using a sharp knife and forceps, an estimate of 10 g pieces was cut. Subsamples were removed for fungal culture. Ten grams (10 g) of the affected yam sample was chop into pieces and soaked in a distilled water. These samples were ready for serially diluted. Nine-millimeter (9 ml) of sterile distilled water were pipetted into the five (5) test tubes. A five (5) fold serial dilution method was adopted.

Preparation of agar and inoculation

Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) was used to culture each yam sample. The Sabouraud dextrose agar was prepared according to the manufacturer's instruction. The preparation of the SDA has been described. Two (2) plates for each location were set for the two yam species each from a yam stand. The prepared agar plate was inoculated with 1ml of the aliquot from 10⁻³ dilution factor and spread evenly. These plates were masked and kept at room temperature (28°C) for 3-5 days. A pure isolate was re-cultured for identification. The morphological identification of the fungal isolates followed a standard identification key in Singh *et al.*, (1991). Identification was done using binocular microscopic identification. A drop of 95% ethanol was first introduced on the middle of a microscopic slide. A fragment of the fungi isolate was gently teased, spread on the slide with an inoculating needle and air dried. Lactophenol blue stained was applied on the dried specimen and a cover slip. The specimen was viewed using X10 and X40 magnification.

Isolation and identification of nematodes

A 4-7 cm length of the yam tubers bought from the study locations was first peeled. Ten grams (10-g) subsamples were taken from each peeled tuber, for nematode collection. Peeled yam was finely chopped into bits. The modified rubber bow techniques for nematodes extraction as described in Coyne *et al.*, (2010 & 2014) were adopted. 10 g of the fine yam samples was placed on a small mesh size filter and placed over a basin half filled with water. The sieve was periodically shaken to soak up the yam samples. The nematodes migrate against the water, pass through the sieve, and settle at the depth of the basin of water. The water was decanted and properly washed to make the nematodes visible.

Nematodes were counted for each yam subsample, and the mean percentage per 10 g of each tuber was estimated according to location. The plant-parasitic nematodes were identified with the aid of a compound microscope at x10 and x40 objective lens. The morphological identification of the plant parasitic nematodes followed standard keys in Siddiqi, (2000).

Data Analysis

Data gathered was expressed as mean ± standard deviation. The stratified significance was determined by ANOVA with the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 20.0. The P-value less than 0.05 implied statistical significance.

RESULTS

The mean percent of nematodes recovered varied across location. Three hundred and thirty-three (333) parasitic nematodes in three genera were recovered and counted from the yam. Out of which, 165 representing 50% were *Scutellonema spp*, 101 (30%) were *Meloidogyne spp* and 67 (20%) were *Pratylenchus spp*. The differences in the species-specific nematodes across the study location were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) Table 1. However, the species-specific nematodes varied across the study locations. While *Scutellonema spp*, was cosmopolitan across all the study location, *Meloidogyne spp* were confine to Tombia, Yenezue-gene and Swali. *Pratylenchus spp* was exclusive to Opolo, Yenezue-gene and Swali. Nevertheless, more *Scutellonema spp*, (80%) were significantly counted in yam from Opolo, while more *Pratylenchus spp* (40.7%) and *Meloidogyne spp* (60.7%) were counted in Yenezue-gene and Tombia respectively (Table 1). The analyzed result had Chi-square (χ^2): 116.03, degrees of freedom (df): 6, and p-value: 1.11×10^{-22} . The very low p-value (< 0.05) indicates a highly significant difference in the distribution of nematode species (*Pratylenchus*, *Meloidogyne*, and *Scutellonema*) across the four locations. This suggests that nematode prevalence is location-dependent.

Table 1: Prevalence of species-specific Yam Nematodes from Selected Yam Stands in Yenagoa Metropolis during March 2023- June 2023

LOCATIONS	Number (%) counted	Number (%) recovered		
		<i>Pratylenchus spp</i>	<i>Meloidogyne spp</i>	<i>Scutellonema spp</i>
Opolo	90(27.0)	18(20.0) ^b	0(0.0) ^c	72(80.0) ^a
Tombia	84(25.2)	0(0.0) ^c	51(60.7) ^a	33(39.3) ^b
Yenezue gene	81(24.3)	33(40.7) ^b	17(21.0) ^c	31(38.3) ^b
Swali	78(23.4)	16(20.5) ^b	33(42.3) ^b	29(37.2) ^b
Total	333(100)	67(20.0) ^c	101(30.0) ^b	165(50.0) ^a

$\chi^2 = 116.03$, $df = 6$, $p < 0.001$. Means with different superscripts (a, b, c) differ significantly at $p < 0.05$ (Tukey HSD).

One hundred and seventy-one (171) fungal colony in four genera and five species were recovered from the yam on the bases of their coloration. The coloration was grayish brown, dark green, dark brown, black & grayish, and Cotton white. The percentage prevalence of the fungi species in order of increasing occurrences is *Aspergillus niger* (25.8%), *Aspergillus flavus* (25.8%), *Alternarium alternata* (19.9%), *Rhizopus stolonifera* (15.2%), and the least was *Penicillium spp* (9.9%). The differences in the species-specific fungi were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The species-specific fungi varied across the study

locations. The differences were not significant ($p > 0.05$). While *Aspergillus flavus* was cosmopolitan across all the study locations, *Aspergillus niger* were confine to Opolo, Tombia, and Swali. *Rhizopus stolonifera* was exclusive in Tombia and Yenezue-gene while *Penicillium spp* were exclusive in Yenezue-gene and Swali. Nevertheless, the prevalence of the individual fungi species across the study location is presented in table 2. More *Rhizopus stolonifera* (41.5%) and *Aspergillus flavus* (39.0%) were found in Yenezue-gene. *Aspergillus niger* (40.5%) and *Altenarium alternata* (38.1%) were exclusive to Opolo. *Aspergillus flavus*, *Altenarium alternata* and *Penicillium spp* were exclusive to yam samples from Swali yam stands. The analyzed results in table 2, had Chi-square (χ^2): 85.12, Degrees of freedom (df): 12, and p-value: 4.32×10^{-13} . The p-value is also much lower than 0.05, showing a statistically significant difference in the distribution of fungi species (*Rhizopus stolonifera*, *Aspergillus niger*, *A. flavus*, *Altenaria alternata*, and *Penicillium spp.*) across locations. This confirms that fungal occurrence is influenced by storage site conditions.

Table 2: Prevalence of species-specific fungi associated with yam rot from Selected Yam Stands in Yenagoa Metropolis during March 2023- June 2023

LOCATIONS	Number (%) counted	Number (%) recovered				
		<i>Rhizopus stolonifera</i>	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	<i>Altenarium alternata</i>	<i>Penicillium spp</i>
Opolo	42(24.6)	0(0.0) ^c	17(40.5) ^a	9(21.4) ^b	16(38.1) ^a	0(0.0) ^c
Tombia	44(25.7)	9(20.5) ^b	17(38.5) ^a	9(20.5) ^b	9(20.5) ^b	0(0.0) ^c
Yenezue gene	41(24.6)	17(41.5) ^c	0(0.0) ^c	16(39.0) ^a	0(0.0) ^c	8(19.5) ^b
Swali	44(25.7)	0(0.0) ^c	17(38.5) ^b	9(20.5) ^b	9(20.5) ^b	9(20.5) ^b
Total	171	26(15.2) ^a	51(25.8) ^b	43(25.2) ^b	34(19.9) ^b	17(9.9) ^c

$\chi^2 = 85.12$, $df = 12$, $p < 0.001$. Means with different superscripts (a, b, c) differ significantly at $p < 0.05$ (Tukey HSD).

DISCUSSION

Nematodes constitute one of the major problems of yam. This is because they can easily survive and multiply in the yam tissues during storage (Okigbo 2004). In this present study, all the yams across the three locations were infested with one or more plant parasitic nematodes. The three species in three genera encountered were *Scutellonema spp* (50%), *Meloidogyne spp* (30%) and *Pratylenchus spp* (20%). The presence of these plant parasitic nematodes has been reported elsewhere as a normal fauna in yam tissues and in soil (Elele, 2021). The presence of the three nematodes in this present study is an indication that the farm where the yam was harvested or the storage room where the yam was kept provided a suitable environment for the growth and proliferation of the nematodes. *Scutellonema spp* has been reported as a common fauna of the yams while *Meloidogyne* was known to be root gall nematodes and *Pratylenchus* as yam lesion nematodes (Adam et al.,2013). The high density of *Scutellonema spp* across the study location is consistent with the report of Hugues (2006) in Benin. However, this present report was at variance with a study elsewhere (Tetteh & Saakwa, 1991) where *Pratylenchus spp* was more abundant than the population of *Meloidogyne* and *Scutellonema spp*. Although the principles of pathogenesis of the Koch's postulate were not demonstrated, the three species of the yam parasitic nematodes have been incriminated as the major causes of yam damage in Nigeria (IITA ,1993)

The differences in the species-specific nematodes across the study location were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The significant differences highlighted that the origin and the sources of the yams as well as the season of harvest, were similar across the study area. In a report by Coyne et al. (2006), a higher proportion of dry rot nematodes was associated with the harvest period. The yams harvested earlier in the dry season were stored longer than yams harvested late. These yams tend to be more exposed to *Scutellonema spp*. than *Meloidogyne* and *Pratylenchus spp*. The high proportion of *Scutellonema spp*. in this present study may highlight the origin of the yam. Although there was no clear indication of the

origin of the yam, studies have shown that *Scutellonema spp* were more associated with the western state of Nigeria (Okigbo, 2004). There were also mixed infections of the three parasitic nematodes in one yam across the locations.

Several fungal colonies in four genera and five species were isolated from yams bought from four locations in the Yenagoa metropolis. The fungi species were *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Alternarium alternata*, *Rhizopus stolonifera* and *Penicillium spp*. The presence of these fungal isolated is an indication that fungi are widespread in the storage room of yam in Yenagoa. The widespread presence of fungi have been reported elsewhere (Ogunleye and Ayansola, 2014). The widespread of fungi varied significantly across the study locations. This variation highlighted the intensity of the yam decay in specific locations and the prevailing conditions surrounding the storage room (Okigbo, et al., 2004). In this present study, *Aspergillus niger* was more predominant on the decayed yam across the locations. The predominancy of *Aspergillus niger* agrees with the reports of Markson, et al. (2012). The activities of the fungi species determined the magnitude of yam decay. Although the toxicity of the individual fungi on the yam in this present study was not tested, studies (Ezeibekwe, Umeoka, & Izuka, 2016) have incriminated *Aspergillus species*, *Fusarium*, *Penicillium*, *Alternarium alternata* and *Rhizopus stolonifera* as agents of yam damage in different parts of Nigeria.

These findings underscore the urgent need for integrated pest management (IPM) strategies that combine nematode control measures, proper yam handling, and improved storage conditions. Future research should focus on sustainable control approaches, including biological control agents, resistant yam varieties, and postharvest treatments to minimize storage losses. Effective implementation of these measures will enhance food security and reduce economic losses among yam farmers and traders in Bayelsa State and across Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

This study has demonstrated that yam rot in *Dioscorea rotundata* within the Yenagoa metropolis is strongly associated with both plant-parasitic nematodes and fungal species. Among the nematodes identified, *Scutellonema spp*. was the most prevalent, followed by *Meloidogyne spp.* and *Pratylenchus spp.*, highlighting their significant role in initiating yam deterioration during storage. Fungal pathogens, including *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Alternaria alternata*, *Rhizopus stolonifer*, and *Penicillium spp.*, were also commonly isolated, with *Aspergillus niger* and *A. flavus* showing higher prevalence across locations. The co-occurrence of nematodes and fungi suggests a synergistic interaction where nematodes create entry points that facilitate fungal colonization, thereby exacerbating tuber decay.

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